

ML-Assisted Ageing Classification of XLPE Power Cables using an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System

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Abstract- The insulation ageing of cross-linked polyethylene (XLPE) power cables affects the reliability of electrical transmission systems. Traditional statistical and empirical models often fail to represent the nonlinear ageing behaviour, and multi-stress environment encountered during cable operation. In this paper, an Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) model is developed for classifying the health index of aged XLPE cables. The ANFIS model's parameters are optimized using sensitivity analysis, and its performance is evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix metrics. The model trained and learned the patterns of aged cables using an existing dataset. Then, the trained model successfully predicted the health index for unlabelled and historical datasets, confirming its robustness and generalization ability. The results indicate that ANFIS effectively handles nonlinear input relationships and offers classification accuracy of more than 98%.

Keywords – Ageing, ANFIS technique, Artificial intelligence method, Generalization, Health assessment, Partial discharge.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cross-linked Polyethylene (XLPE) insulated power cables, as shown in Fig. 1, are crucial for reliable and efficient power transmission due to their high insulation resistance, dimensional stability, low dissipation factor, and high dielectric strength [1]. Although designed for over 30 years of service, system faults, primarily due to ageing, often reduce their lifespan [2]. The insulation ageing is a major factor in cable lifetime evaluation, causing material property changes and breakdown. The XLPE insulations are susceptible to ageing influenced by morphology, additives, oxidation, ions, and water [3]. Deterioration is accelerated by thermal, electrical, mechanical and environmental stresses. Table 1 details various factors affecting XLPE insulation [4]. Consequently, assessing cable condition is crucial for reliable operation.

The ageing indicators like partial discharge (PD), space charge, insulation resistance (IR), and dielectric loss [5] can be measured through offline or online techniques. Destructive offline tests like AC/DC withstand voltage and IR tests contrast with non-damaging online methods such as PD and low-frequency monitoring [6]. These parameters are used for ageing prediction via models like the inverse power law and Arrhenius model [7]. However, single-parameter methods are often insufficient to accurately reflect cable ageing due to the complex, multi-stress environment of real-world operation.

Fig. 1. The structure of XLPE underground power cables.

Table 1. Different ageing aspects and ageing causes of them.

Aspect	Causes
Electrical	Operating and transient voltage (AC, DC, impulse) – Current – Frequency – PD – Charge injection
Thermal	Maximum and ambient temperatures - Temperature gradient - Temperature cycling
Mechanical	Bending – Tension – Compression – Torsion – Vibration - Compression cycle
Environmental	Gases - Water/humidity - Corrosive chemicals – Lubricants - Radiation

To address these challenges, various AI techniques have been applied to predict XLPE power cable ageing. For example, authors in [8] developed an eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) model, enhanced with a partial swarm optimizer (PSO) for condition assessment using parameters like PD, age, operating age or life, and corrosion. In another paper, the health status is classified by using standard and fuzzy-based support vector machine (SVM), showing high accuracy but suffering from random sampling in small datasets [9]. To overcome this problem and bringing ability to remove additional feature, authors in [10] proposed an SVM combined with PSO, leading to better performance. Many studies conducted the same approach with different algorithms to classify the stage of ageing, such as Naïve Bayes, neural networks, K-nearest neighbours, decision trees, random forests, and CatBoost [11-13]. While these methods offer reasonable accuracy and speed, they each have limitations. For instance, SVM-based methods suffer from dealing with nonlinear problems, and tree-based techniques face problems such as limited robustness to environmental and operational changes, low interpretability, reliance on input feature quality, and poor generalizability.

Unlike the statistical approach of SVM or the decision-boundary focus of tree-based methods, adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) was chosen to leverage the advantages of both neural networks in learning complex

mappings and fuzzy logic in providing interpretable rules for classifying cable health conditions [14]. This paper presents an ANFIS to classify the health index of XLPE power cables, implemented using fuzzy c-mean (FCM) and subtractive clustering method (SCM). Sensitivity analysis was used to optimize its hyperparameters. The optimized ANFIS model was then applied to a dataset with unlabelled historical data to predict the health index, addressing a gap in previous studies regarding robustness and adaptability to new inputs.

II. ANFIS MODELLING FOR CABLE AGEING PREDICTION

The ANFIS is a hybrid artificial intelligence model that integrates neural networks with fuzzy logic (based on Sugano fuzzy inference systems) to create an adaptive system capable of handling nonlinear relationships between inputs and outputs. The structure of ANFIS comprises five layers that function sequentially to process inputs, apply fuzzy inference, and compute the final output [15], as depicted in Fig. 2. The membership functions and rules have been defined using clustering methods, such as fuzzy c-mean method (FCM) and subtractive clustering method (SCM) in order to improve the performance of the model [16]. Based on Fig. 2, each layer of ANFIS has specific properties. In the first layer, inputs $x_{i=1,\dots,5}$ (i.e. age, PD, loading, visual condition, and neutral corrosion) are applied for fuzzification through membership functions like the Gaussian function as follows [14],

$$O_{ij}^1 = e^{-\frac{(x_i - k_{ij})^2}{2\sigma_{ij}^2}} \quad (1)$$

where i and j represent the number of inputs and fuzzy sets, respectively. k_{ij} and σ_{ij} are the centre and standard deviation of the Gaussian function. The second layer, determines the firing strength of each fuzzy rule by applying the T-norm operation (a fuzzy “AND” or “OR” operator that combines the degrees of truth of the input fuzzy sets) as follows [15],

$$O_i^2 = w_i = \prod_j O_{ij}^1, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

In the third layer, known as the normalization layer, the normalized firing strengths \bar{w}_i are calculated as follows [15]:

$$O_i^3 = \bar{w}_i = \frac{w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

where \bar{w}_i is the proportion of the firing strength relative to the total firing strength.

The defuzzification layer computes the contribution of each rule in which for the first-order Sugeno system is calculated as [16],

$$O_i^4 = \bar{w}_i f_i = \bar{w}_i \left(\sum_{i=1}^{n+1} p_i x_i + p_0 \right) \quad (4)$$

where p_i represents the coefficient corresponding to the i^{th} input variable and p_0 is the bias term. The final layer, computes the overall output of the ANFIS model by aggregating the outputs from the previous layer as follows [14-16],

$$O^5 = \sum_{i=1}^n O_i^4 \quad (5)$$

The input layer, to obtain the parameters of the fuzzy sets, different methods such as FCM and SCM can be used.

Fig. 2. The ageing assessment of XLPE cable using ANFIS model.

Table 2. The clustering methods used for membership function generation [16].

Method	Formula	Details
FCM	$J = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^C u_{ij}^m \ x_i - c_j\ ^2$	u_{ij}^m : Degree of membership of x_i in cluster j . m : Fuzziness parameter. c_j : Cluster center. $\ \cdot\ $: Euclidean distance.
SCM	$P(x_i) = \sum_{j=1}^N e^{-\frac{\ x_i - c_j\ ^2}{\alpha}}$	$P(x_i)$: Potential of x_i . α : Control parameter of c_j influence.

In Table 2, a summary of each method is presented, where FCM assigns membership degrees to data points based on their distance to cluster centres and SCM selects cluster centres based on data density, with the potential function determining the centre.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the field samples, a dataset including features such as age, PD, neutral corrosion, visual conditions and loading status of the XLPE cables has been constructed [17]. It contains the details of 2500 cables in four years during two decades, commencing from 2003. To some extents, the operational age indicates cable condition defects, and as cables age, their insulation performance diminishes over time. By measuring PD over time, the performance of the insulations was obtained. According to different merits like good, medium, and poor, the visual conditions of cables reported, and because they were buried underground for a long time, they got affected by corrosion, as a result of long exposure to water and mud. Finally, the cables' peak current is measured, as it can accelerate the ageing.

The visual conditions of the cables are labels and need to be translated from (good, medium, poor) to (2, 1, 0) to be used in the classification of health indexes. Based on the dataset, the cables' health condition has been classified into 5 indexes (i.e., 1, 2, 3, 4, 5) in the year 2018, considering 1 (H_1) as the worst condition and 5 (H_5) as the best condition. The proportion of cable samples assigned to each health index in the dataset is: 15% (H_1), 16% (H_2), 28% (H_3), 22% (H_4), and 19% (H_5). The ANFIS model does not require encoding the health condition, as the model recognizes the indexes itself. The ANFIS model inherently performs the normalization, which reduces the burden of pre-normalizing the input samples.

The performance of the model is evaluated through multiple metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix. Each of the performance metrics can be calculated based on the counts of true positives (TP), false positives (FP), false negatives (FN), and true negatives (TN) for each class. To illustrate how these are visualized for a specific

Table 3. The ANFIS model hyperparameters according to sensitivity analysis for SCM and FCM clustering methods.

Parameter	Range	Accuracy (%)	Best
ANFIS-SCM			
CIR	[0.05:0.01:0.95]	98.13	0.5
NP	[100:10:2000]	98.13	500
SS	[0.05:0.01:1]	98.13	0.1
ANFIS-FCM			
NC	[2:1:20]	97.33	10
NP	[20:10:2000]	97.33	400
IRSZ	[0.1:0.05:1]	97.87	0.4

		Predicted Classes				
		H ₁	H ₂	H ₃	H ₄	H ₅
Actual Classes	H ₁	TN	FP	TN		
	H ₂					
	H ₃	FN	TP	FN		
	H ₄	TN	FP	TN		
	H ₅					

Fig. 3. The visualized confusion matrix of class No. 3 (H₃) based on true positives (TP), false positives (FP), false negatives (FN), and true negatives (TN).

Fig. 4. The 5-fold cross validation of ANFIS model with SCM clustering method.

class, Fig. 3 presents the confusion matrix with H₃ considered as the positive class. Therefore, the metrics can be calculated based on (6) to (7).

$$Accuracy = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^C (TP_i + TN_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^C (TP_i + TN_i + FP_i + FN_i)} \quad (8)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FP_i} \quad (9)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP_i}{FP_i + FN_i} \quad (10)$$

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (11)$$

The evaluations have been done via MATLAB 2024b with 32 GB RAM and i7 CPU. The dataset is split into training (70% of total data in dataset), validating (15%) and testing (15%) datasets. The hyperparameters of the model are presented in Table 3, which are obtained through the sensitivity analysis method for the ANFIS model with SCM and FCM clustering methods. For this optimization, the most important controlling parameters of each clustering methods were selected for evaluation. In the SCM method, cluster influence range (CIR), number of epochs (NP), and step size (SS) were chosen. The same parameters for FCM are evaluated; with the number of clusters (NC) instead of CIR. After optimization of control parameters, the models underwent 5-fold cross-validation to ensure their correct performance across the dataset and also, their ability regarding generalization. The accuracy of each fold is depicted in Fig. 4, showing stable accuracy in different folds.

Fig. 5. (a) The predicted classes using ANFIS with SCM method and (b) the confusion matrix of the model for different classes.

Fig. 6. (a) The predicted classes using ANFIS with SCM method and (b) the confusion matrix of the model for different classes on the unseen dataset.

Fig. 7. The results of health index prediction using ANFIS with SCM method on historical datasets of different years: (a) 2003, (b) 2008, (c) 2013.

The standard deviation is calculated as 0.0092, presenting low variations of the model's performance across all folds.

The result of the model for health index classification on the 2018 cable dataset is presented in Fig. 5a. It is evident from this figure that the model classified H₁, H₄, and H₅ with 100% accuracy. For H₂ and H₃, the model's accuracy was 89.8% and 99%, respectively, showing a slight confusion between these two indexes. The confusion matrix of the model for the same results is presented in Fig. 5b, which shows the same results and distribution of the classified samples with a low confusion between H₂ and H₃. In order to ensure the performance of the model, the 2018 cable dataset is split into main (80%) and unseen (20%) datasets and the prediction result is depicted in Fig. 6. It can be concluded that the model is capable of classifying unseen data, effectively.

Fig. 8. (a) The predicted classes using ANFIS with FCM method and (b) the confusion matrix of this model for classification on the unseen dataset.

Table 4. The comparison between SCM and FCM clustering methods for ANFIS model based on 2018 cable dataset.

Model	Acc.	Pre.	Rec.	F1	Training time	Testing time	
ANFIS	FCM	97.87	97.72	97.94	97.82	12.70s	0.0013s
	SCM	98.13	97.77	98.52	98.10	22.49s	0.0018s

As a next step, the cable datasets of 2003, 2008, and 2013 have been fed to the trained and established ANFIS ageing model for predicting the health index of cables in historical dataset (Fig. 7). The model's predictions on the historical data (2003-2013) exhibit a clear trend correlating with cable ageing. The proportion of samples classified as hazardous increased over time, with 15% reaching the most severe condition by 2018, which implies that the established ANFIS model effectively captured the temporal dynamics of cable ageing. The proposed method dealt with the nonlinearity of the dataset appropriately and showed excellent accuracy and generalization ability in learning from existing dataset for unseen samples classification that had been missing from previous studies analysis on different AI models [8-13].

The performance metrics of ANFIS with FCM and SCM methods, together with their training and testing time have been presented in

Table 4 and compared with each other.

The performance of the ANFIS model with the FCM method regarding the classification of different classes on 2018 dataset is presented in Fig. 8. The confusion matrix shows similar accuracy for class H_1 , H_3 and H_3 , but confusion on the other classes, which may arise from the different distribution of the samples. It is clear that the ANFIS model with SCM algorithm as a clustering method for membership function production has better performance than the ANFIS with FCM.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, an ANFIS technique was implemented for health index classification of aged 15kV XLPE underground power cables. By using fuzzy c-mean (FCM) and subtractive (SCM) clustering methods, the performance of the ANFIS for classifying and predicting health index of aged cables were presented under different conditions. Based on the results, it is evident that the ANFIS model could bring proper classification for the health index of cable with an accuracy of more than 98% and produce new labels for historical datasets. For future work, we intend to develop a model for prediction of next years of ageing in these cables based on the existing dataset. A

benchmark of different AI techniques will be presented for a better understanding of all models on the same dataset.

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